

REALIZATION OF INTEGRATIVE APPROACH AT THE LESSONS OF LITERATURE IN THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *The article highlights the problems of integrative relations in literature lessons in the modern educational space, emphasizing the types of integration of both external and internal nature. The author has developed the concept of formation of cultural competence of students, based on the theory of integration, on the idea of literary education as an integral system. In the course of the research the methods, forms and technologies aimed at the implementation of the content lines of the methodological system are defined and described (integrated lessons of different types; analysis and interpretation of works of art selected by analogy with the studied text in terms of themes, problems, visual and expressive means; creation and use of integrative cultural commentary; organization of individual, group and collective integrative activities of students; integrated test, etc.).*

Achieving the goal set by the author requires defining new educational approaches, changing the strategy of teaching subjects, among which a special role belongs to literature.

Considerable attention is paid to the specifics of the organization of the process of literary education, corresponding to the challenges of the time, dictates the need to implement an integrative approach. The author concludes that it is the integrative approach in teaching literature that can bring significant positive changes in the pedagogical practice of modern school and contribute to the solution of key educational tasks.

Keywords: *modern educational process, integration, literature lesson, association, system, teaching tool.*

Аннотация. *В статье освещены проблемы интегративных связей на уроках литературы в современном образовательном пространстве, особо отмечаются типы интеграции как внешнего, так и внутреннего характера. Автором разработана концепция формирования культурологической компетенции студентов, базирующаяся на теории интеграции, на представлении о литературном образовании как об интегральной системе. В ходе исследования определены и описаны методы, формы и технологии, направленные на реализацию содержательных линий методической системы (интегрированные уроки различного типа; анализ и интерпретация произведений искусства, подобранных по аналогии с изучаемым текстом по тематике, проблематике, образительно выразительным средствам; создание и использование интегративного культурологического комментария; организация индивидуальной, групповой и коллективной интегративной деятельности учащихся; интегрированный зачет и др.).*

Достижение поставленной автором цели требует определения новых образовательных подходов, изменения стратегии преподавания учебных предметов, среди которых особая роль принадлежит литературе.

Значительное внимание уделяется специфике организации процесса литературного образования, соответствующего вызовам времени, диктует необходимость реализации интегративного подхода. Автор приходит к выводу, что именно интегративный подход в преподавании литературы способен внести существенные позитивные изменения в

педагогическую практику современной школы и содействовать решению ключевых воспитательных задач.

Ключевые слова: современный образовательный процесс, интеграция, урок литературы, объединение, система, средство обучения.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada zamonaviy ta'lim makonidagi adabiyot darolarida integrativ aloqalar muammolari yoritilgan, tashqi va ichki xarakterdagi integratsiya turlari alohida qayd etilgan. Muallif integratsiya nazariyasiga, adabiy ta'limni integral tizim sifatida taqdim etishga asoslangan talabalarning madaniy kompetensiyasini shakllantirish konsepsiyasini ishlab chiqdi. Maqolada uslubiy tizimning mazmunli yo'nalishlarini amalga oshirishga qaratilgan usullar, shakllar va texnologiyalar aniqlanadi va tavsiflanadi; mavzular, muammolar, tasviriy ekspressiv vositalar bo'yicha o'rganilayotgan matnga o'xshashlik bilan tanlangan san'at asarlarini tahlil qilish va talqin etish; integrativ madaniy sharhni yaratish va ulardan foydalanish; talabalarning individual, guruh va jamoaviy integrativ faoliyatini tashkillashtirish bayon etilgan.

Muallif tomonidan qo'yilgan maqsadga erishish yangi ta'lim yondashuvlarini aniqlashni, o'quv fanlarini o'qitish strategiyasini o'zgartirishni talab qiladi, ular orasida adabiyot alohida o'rin tutadi. Vaqt muammolariga mos keladigan adabiy ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga katta e'tibor qaratilib, integral yondashuvni amalga oshirish zarurligini taqozo etadi. Maqolada adabiyotni o'qitishda integrativ yondashuv zamonaviy maktabning pedagogik amaliyotiga sezilarli ijobiy o'zgarishlar kiritishi va asosiy ta'lim muammolarini hal qilishga yordam berishi mumkinligi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy o'quv jarayoni, integratsiya, adabiyot darsi, birlashma, tizim, o'qitish vositasi.

Introduction. A productive way to transform and improve the quality of the educational process in the educational process, to eliminate the contradiction between the ever-increasing flow of knowledge and the specificity of its assimilation contains an integrative way of presenting information. Such pedagogical phenomenon as integration helps to overcome the fragmentary and mosaic way of perception of knowledge by students, provides an opportunity to master the complex knowledge, the established order of moral values of man, forms in them an integral universal picture of the world, educates young people's own view of the environment. In modern times, the ever-increasing volume of information imposes a sharp decline in the possibility of its perception, assimilation and reproduction. Therefore, in recent decades, pedagogy has addressed the issue of systematic presentation of structured knowledge, which is a certain, clearly developed complex. The future of the educational process is seen in the interdisciplinary connection of academic disciplines, in their synthesis, in the development of integrative courses in the field of humanitarian knowledge, in its interpenetration and complementarity. Integration implies mutual coordination of the content of education in different academic disciplines, the construction and selection of material, which are determined both by the general goals of education and the optimal consideration of educational and educational tasks, conditioned by the specificity of each academic subject.

Many foreign (J.A. Comensky, I.G. Pestalozzi, J. Locke, I. Herbart, A. Disterverg) and domestic (K.D. Ushinsky, V.I. Vodovozov, V.P. Ostrogorsky, I.F. Annensky, V.N. Maksimova, A.Y. Danilyuk, etc.) educators and scientists of different epochs addressed the problem of integration in education.

Emphasizing the necessity of linking knowledge between academic subjects for the formation of students' knowledge and ensuring the integrity of the learning process, J.A. Comensky wrote: "As in nature everything is connected one with another, so in teaching it is necessary to connect everything one with another in such a way and not otherwise" [3, p.88]. I.G. Pestalozzi also emphasized the necessity of interconnection of educational subjects, because it is in such a connection - they are in nature [12, p.26]. A. Distverg emphasized the necessity of interdisciplinary links for systematic, thorough study of all subjects at school. In his opinion, the establishment of a natural and reasonable connection between academic subjects is of great importance for the formation of complete and deep knowledge, skills and abilities [5, p.58].

There are many definitions of the phenomenon of integration - it is the restoration of unity, unification of parts into a whole, the process of integrity formation, the state of connectivity of individual differentiated parts and functions of a system, organism into a whole, as well as the process leading to such a state. The above definitions provide only a general scientific interpretation of the concept of "integration", as they do not specify what kind of unifying elements we are talking about. Moreover, it is not clear from them what integration is - a state, a process or a result of integration.

Integration, its ideas and methodology are increasingly penetrating into university practice. Its goal is to unite, merge all parts into a single whole, qualitatively new. Consequently, in order to acquire and preserve a qualitatively significant system of knowledge and universal values, for the so-called entry into a certain cultural era, for the possibility of dialog with it, for the introduction into the picture of the world, to determine the presence of man in it, his presence in different symbols, images, models, schemes of being, it is necessary to establish a deep connection, which should be based on common scientific ideas, concepts, rules and inherent formulas. The solution of this task in the modern educational space, in our opinion, is facilitated by integration, which allows us to give a holistic view of man, his cultural, historical and social significance. "The essence of integration in teaching contains two meanings: firstly, it is the creation of students' holistic view of the surrounding world (here integration is considered as a learning goal); secondly, it is finding a common platform of convergence of subject knowledge (here integration is a means of learning)" [7, p. 16]. "Such phenomenon as integration appeared, first of all, against the background of its opposite - differentiation of sciences and their branches, growing volume of knowledge and requirements to them in each branch, leading to deepening of specialization in sciences and within sciences, inevitable at deepening narrowing of the circle of professional interests of narrow specialists. Thus, integration between academic subjects does not negate the subject system. It is a possible way to improve it, overcoming shortcomings and is aimed at deepening the interrelationships and interdependencies between subjects" [10, p. 24]. The modern educational space is aimed at the education of a highly educated, intellectually developed personality, who has a holistic, in-depth knowledge of the world picture and understands the relationship between the phenomena and processes that represent this picture. The fragmentation of educational material and the way of presenting information is the main and, perhaps, the main reason for the mosaic and scattered worldview of the student, the lack of interconnected knowledge in the branch of economic, political, cultural, information education.

Materials and methods. In the process of research the following research methods were used: theoretical (study of scientific literature, analysis of educational programs, educational and methodological and literary works, classification, generalization and systematization, etc.) and

empirical (observation of the educational process, questionnaires and conversations with teachers, students), conducting and analysis of test works, conducting a training and test experiment).

Results. In practice, there are cases when complex sciences become a source of integration. Thus, for example, in a literature lesson, when studying V.G. Rasputin's novel "Live and Remember", the teacher presents not only literary commentary, but also uses information from history, cultural studies, and Russian language. In practice, the teacher, using this theory, relies on knowledge from all kinds of arts to recreate an in-depth and complementary idea of the historical epoch, cultural space, artistic image, worldview paradigm, thus trying to activate various receptors of students. In this approach, all human psychophysical mechanisms complement each other. For example, using musical works in literature lessons, the teacher induces auditory perceptions in the student. The use of painting in lessons "connects" visual receptors to the work. When transferring knowledge from the field of architecture, it is possible to familiarize the child with the spatial content of the thought process.

Consequently, a holistic picture of the surrounding world is created. When studying a literary work, the integrated use of knowledge from different types of art allows to convey the author's idea most fully and synthesize the acquired skills, including in the interaction the feeling and emotional background of the learner. The practical significance of the application of this method of work at the lesson of literature is to form a connection between emotional and thinking (cognitive) activity.

Thus, in influencing the child's mind, the teacher should put forward fundamental ideas that will allow the student to form a holistic picture of the world. The sequence of using such ideas allows the child to create supporting synthesized knowledge. Consequently, the scientific and practical significance of integrated lessons in the modern educational process is simply undeniable. The next type of connections at the lesson of literature can be used quite often, as it combines the features of both sequential and parallel integration. The mixed type of integration connection is characterized by the fact that it can include integrative connection of literature, architecture, fine arts, music, etc.

The integrative connection of the mixed type is most often used in practice, as it has a more flexible structure and allows complex and systematic involvement of material from different types of arts, involving some concepts, ideas, concepts of other educational subjects, but preserving the originality of literature as a learning space. Thus, in practice, a lesson of this type activates the student's thinking processes and provides an opportunity to get the most complete, holistic picture of a work of fiction, i.e. a literary work is the main component of the lesson. Thanks to the analysis of the artistic text, the student gets additional knowledge from history, theory of literature, music, architecture, painting.

Discussion. The described three types of integrative links in the literature lesson have been actively used by teachers in practice recently in practice. Literature is the main link of such lessons. A specific work gives an opportunity to build a historical-literary, historical-cultural context in the minds of students. "At such a lesson, when studying a particular work or theme, information from a wide variety of subjects and arts is attracted, which supplement, clarify, develop the literary material, refract it into new ideas, images, concepts, pictures. The lesson structure resembles a "daisy", in the center of which is the literary text, and its "petals" are the material of other subjects, united at the level of content, methods and forms of activity" [6, p. 96]. The fragments of analysis of R. Gamzatov's poem that we have offered clearly show the areas of other subjects that are used in the literature lesson: history - material about the Great Patriotic War; cartography - geographical

map of the country, the scale of the defeat, political, economic and cultural ties with other states of Europe and Asia; music - historical monuments of verbal content; history of literature - connection and presence of works about the Great Patriotic War, establishment of intercultural contact and identity of the symbol of the Great Patriotic War; art - interconnection and presence of works about the Great Patriotic War, the establishment of intercultural contact and the identity of the symbol of the cranes; art - interrelation of literature and cinematography. This type of lesson implies the activation of receptive and cognitive activity of students.

Conclusion. The ideas of integration in improving, enhancing and improving the quality of teaching and educational function of modern education are extremely fruitful. Synergetic approach of integrative learning is productive within the framework of modern educational space, reflects modern trends in the development of fundamental natural sciences and humanities, acts as a philosophical basis for their convergence and interaction. basis of their convergence and interaction. Association, interaction, interpenetration of subjects, creation of integrated programs, courses, various types of lessons significantly improves the educational process and is welcomed in pedagogical theory and practice. "This process is characteristic for all subjects, but first of all for the lessons of literature, the art of word, which can truly realize its huge aesthetic and moral and philosophical potential of impact on the recipient's consciousness only in cooperation with other arts, other related humanitarian subjects" [6, p. 92].

In conclusion, we can conclude that the appearance of such a lesson in the educational process is necessary because:

First, integration in modern society explains the need for integration in education. Modern society needs well-trained specialists of a wide profile, possessing systemic and functional knowledge about the world, the place of man in it. Integration in education contributes to the fulfillment of this need.

Secondly, students cognize the surrounding world in unity, integrity, while the subjects of the school cycle do not give an idea of the whole phenomenon, fragmenting it into disparate fragments.

Thirdly, integrated lessons develop the potential of students themselves, encourage active cognition of the surrounding reality, development of logic, thinking, communicative abilities.

Fourthly, integrated lessons, due to switching to a variety of activities, increase cognitive interest, serve to develop students' attention, thinking, speech.

Fifthly, integration provides an opportunity for self-realization and self-expression of the teacher.

In the process of studying works of fiction, students acquire the ability to understand literature as an art form in relation to other art forms (music, theater, painting, cinema), acquire the experience of understanding their content in relationship with the cultural environment, with the basic national values that determine the self-consciousness of the people, the priorities of social and personal development, the nature of a person's relationship to family, society, state, work, comprehend the meaning of human life, acquire personal, family and social culture. The specificity of the organization of the process of literary education, corresponding to the challenges of the time, dictates the need to implement an integrative approach. It is the integrative approach to teaching literature that can bring significant positive changes in the pedagogical practice of modern education and contribute to the solution of key educational tasks.

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